

TEACHING METHODS IN ENGLISH

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Annotation: Teaching needs to encompass two main elements sending and receiving information. Ultimately, an instructor tries his satisfactory to impart understanding the way he understood it. The use of innovative methods in instructional establishments is attainable now not only to improve education, but also to empower people, reinforce governance, and galvanize the effort to reap the human improvement aim for the US with a wide variety of instructional alternatives on hand before the current generation learners, the more recent trends seem to have emerged in the subject of education that have completely changed the face of the ordinary device of education. Recent trends, methodologies, and tendencies portray the vital position of the schooling zone in regularly occurring with its internalization of the training process, stress on excellence above quantity, bigger adoption of technologies, a necessity for professional talent, etc.

Keywords: New devices, methods, ICT, learning process, pedagogy, Suggestopedia, Approach

INTRODUCTION

Language has been and will stay the key to the world of knowledge. Proficiency in multiple languages has been valued since ancient times. At every stage of the improvement of society, a certain language plays an important role for all mankind. Knowledge of foreign languages opens new doorways for a person to improve himself and increase his worldview. If before information of the German language used to be required, today English performs a prominent role. The capacity to communicate English properly is intently associated with its teaching. The cutting-edge age requires a new approach and new methods of teaching overseas languages. To awaken in the child they wish to learn, to accumulate new knowledge and activities, whilst building the further course of their education, is the main intention of the present day school. The college students are tasked with independently studying, finding, and inspecting materials, while the most important task of the instructor is the proper direction. The

teacher wishes to logically and effectively build a lesson so that students are interested in learning English, since the practice of the traditional method, forcing students to cram words, and grammar in practice did not provide the desired result.

Theoretical review: The search for new instructing strategies is associated with a lack of motivation among students to research English. Very often, there is no advantageous motivation, because when learning an overseas language, students come upon some difficulties and no longer analyze the fabric due to their psychological characteristics. Work experience suggests that the use of various, modern, sparkling sources and means provokes students' interest, will increase their motivation to study.

Teaching strategies - the method of interaction between the trainer and students, as a result of which the transfer and assimilation of knowledge, skills, and competencies provided for by the content material of training happen [1,p.85]. It ought to be cited that the teaching method is a complex, systemic formation, which is characterized by the aid of all the aspects that underlie the classification. The methodology of teaching a foreign language, in turn, is a set of methods, methods, and teaching techniques aimed at studying a foreign language.

ICT (Information and communication technology). According to the results of the statistics analysis, the college students used ICT tools to analyze ESP, but not yet optimally. There are three classes of ICT used in English for Special Purposes (ESP) learning employing agribusiness students. They are ICT as academic resources, ICT for organization of educational manner and communication. As learning resources, they consist of learning about programs, online resources, and video resources.

Compared to these three learning resources, video sources have been typically used by students in the context of studying ESP, followed through online sources and instructional programs. Students suggested that the video resources have been very useful, comprehensible, and effortless to access. The quantity of online fabric and resources on YouTube is huge and following YouTube statistics, YouTube is the greatest Video portal and the 2nd greatest video search engine with a huge variety of videos accessible on all topics and in many languages. In fact, via learning through YouTube, ESP college students have discovered a lot of technical vocabulary related to the spelling, meaning, pronunciation, and description of these words.

Grammar Translation Method. The grammar–translation method is a method of educating overseas languages derived from the classical (sometimes referred to as traditional) technique of teaching Ancient Greek and Latin. In grammar–translation classes, students learn grammatical rules and then follow those regulations

by translating sentences between the goal language and the native language. Advanced college students might also be required to translate complete texts word-for-word. The method has two primary goals: to allow students to examine and translate literature written in the supply language and to further students' normal mental development.

Audio lingual. The audio-lingual method or Army Method is an approach used in teaching foreign languages. It is based totally on behaviorist theory, which postulates that certain characteristics of living things, and in this case humans, could be skilled through a machine of reinforcement. The right use of a trait would acquire advantageous remarks whilst unsuitable use of that trait would receive negative feedback. This method of language getting to know was comparable to another method called the direct method. Like the direct method, the audio-lingual approach cautioned that students ought to be taught a language directly, besides using the student's native language to explain new phrases or grammar in the goal language. However, unlike the direct method, the audio-lingual method did not center attention on teaching vocabulary. Rather, the instructor drilled college students in the use of grammar.

Suggestopedia. Suggestopedia is a pedagogic gadget of teaching, which is a combination of pedagogy, psychology, and artistic approaches.

To understand what suggestopedia is and why it is the method that leads to the best and most long-lasting results, the important variations from regular forms of schooling be outlined.

Natural Approach. The Natural Approach is the approach of 2nd language learning that focuses on verbal exchange competencies and language exposure before rules and grammar, comparable to how you examine your first language. This approach highlights comprehensible and significant practice activities and introduces the language learner to an extraordinary deal of vocabulary at the commencing as a substitute for the production of grammatically best sentences. The basic rules for implementing this technique consist of no longer usage of the learners' native language and no longer referring to grammatical explanations. The language is seen as an automobile for communicating meanings and messages.

Conclusion

Each of the exclusive strategies has contributed new elements and has attempted to deal with some problems of language learning. However, they derived in a special historical context, pressured exclusive social and academic needs, and have special theoretical considerations. Therefore, in instructing practice, to follow

these strategies effectively and efficiently, practitioners must take these questions in mind: who the learners are, what their current degree of language talent is, what kind of communicative wants they have, and the circumstances in which they will be the use of English in the future, and so on. In a word, no single technique could guarantee profitable results.

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